

Dynamic UAV Deployment in Multi-UAV Wireless Networks: A Multimodal-Feature-Based Deep Reinforcement Learning Approach

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Abstract—The use of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) as aerial base stations has attracted increasing research interest in recent years. A key challenge in this field is determining how to deploy multiple UAVs in dynamic environments, particularly where mobile user demands fluctuate. To address this challenge, this article presents an adaptive UAV deployment scheme in a dynamic multi-UAV wireless network, considering the mobility of UAVs and users, state variability, and adjustable UAV transmission power. By jointly optimizing the UAVs' operational modes, transmission power levels, and movement strategies, our objective is to achieve a tradeoff between minimizing power consumption and maximizing ground user coverage. A deep reinforcement learning (DRL) approach is proposed to address these challenges. To capture the dynamic variations of users and UAVs in the environment, a multimodal feature state space is designed, consisting of both a multichannel image and vectors. The image component integrates real-time data on user distribution and the UAV coverage area, while the vectors represent UAV operational modes, position data, and system temporal information. These multimodal features are processed using a combination of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and multilayer perceptrons (MLPs) for advanced feature extraction. To enhance training stability and efficiency, the proposed approach updates parameters using the proximal policy optimization (PPO) method. Simulation results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed scheme in balancing power consumption and coverage while effectively managing system dynamics.

Index Terms—Deep reinforcement learning (DRL), dynamic deployment, energy efficiency, multimodal feature extraction, unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) network.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE INTEGRATION of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) into wireless communication networks has attracted significant interest in recent years [1]. Serving as aerial base

stations, UAVs with communication and computing capabilities, can boost the development of numerous applications such as the Internet of Things (IoT) [2], mobile edge computing [3], emergency network construction [4], and terrestrial network infrastructure enhancement [5]. A key aspect of UAV effectiveness in these roles is the rapid and flexible deployment abilities, which are vital for enabling dynamic network adaptation and broadening service coverage.

The advantages of UAV flexible deployment have led to their widespread use in various scenarios. However, efficient and dynamic deployment of UAVs for service provisioning also faces significant challenges [6]. Dynamic UAV deployment involves considerations such as placement, trajectory planning [7], and adjustment of coverage areas [8], which directly impact the system objectives in UAV networks, such as latency, energy efficiency, and quality of service. Furthermore, UAV deployment is not a one-time event but is instead adaptive and variable. Due to changing environmental conditions and user needs, UAV networks must adjust over time, even anticipating user activities to make optimal decisions promptly [9]. Overall, it necessitates finding efficient and flexible UAV network deployment strategies based on set objectives such as maximizing energy efficiency, optimizing user experience, and minimizing latency. This represents a multiobjective optimization problem and a decision-making issue involving various UAV deployment actions. Such challenges often involve dynamic, time-varying, and complex network system modeling, as well as the optimization of problems with multiple constraints and objectives, which are typically nondeterministic polynomial-time (NP)-hard problems. Additionally, ongoing technological advancements, such as the development of 5G and beyond wireless networks, impose increasingly stringent requirements on UAV deployments [10]. Given these challenges, innovative approaches are required to manage the high dynamism and complexity effectively.

Traditional optimization methods, such as genetic algorithms (GAs) and particle swarm optimization (PSO), are effective for static or single-instance tasks, such as path planning, where the objective is to identify a fixed optimal solution. However, their inherent limitations in adapting to dynamic and continuously evolving conditions diminish their suitability for real-time adaptive scenarios. Consequently, these methods are less appropriate for UAV network applications, which

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require sequential decision-making in response to changing environmental and network states. Recognizing these limitations, recent research has increasingly turned to reinforcement learning (RL), which has demonstrated its superior decision-making capabilities across various complex UAV network applications [11]. Unlike conventional machine learning algorithms, RL excels by learning through direct interactions with the environment, continuously adjusting and optimizing strategies based on feedback [12]. Such adaptability makes RL particularly suitable for dynamic UAV deployment scenarios. Deep RL (DRL) further enhances RL's potential by incorporating deep learning techniques, such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) [13] and multilayer perceptrons (MLPs) [14], to approximate value functions and policies in high-dimensional state and action spaces. These networks enable DRL to capture complex patterns and dependencies of environment information, allowing for more effective decision-making. Offline training [15] and transfer learning [16] enable DRL-based models to adapt to real-world applications, such as UAV racing [17]. Moreover, advanced algorithms like actor-critic (AC) [18] and proximal policy optimization (PPO) [19] are used to stabilize DRL training, enhance exploration, and accelerate convergence, equipping DRL to manage complex decision-making and optimization tasks in dynamic UAV networks effectively. Despite these advancements, tailoring DRL agent state information and training methods to different scenarios remains a challenge, requiring adaptation to specific UAV network dynamics.

A. Related Work

Deployment and coverage strategies are highly related to the overall performance of UAV networks, necessitating their optimization across various UAV applications. Kuang et al. [20] enhanced the task offloading capabilities in UAV-assisted edge computing networks by jointly optimizing 3-D UAV deployment and computational resource allocation. Han et al. [21] employed clustering and iterative methods to optimize UAV deployment and trajectory, minimizing power consumption during IoT data collection tasks. Wang et al. [22] designed a UAV deployment and association scheme based on statistical user locations in UAV-assisted terrestrial cellular networks, aiming to reduce transmission power consumption. Prasad and Ramkumar [23] proposed a UAV base station-enabled emergency communication network that optimizes UAV deployment and trajectory to enhance user coverage, increase channel capacity, and reduce power consumption and latency. Designing fixed UAV deployment strategies is insufficient for variable environments that require real-time task adaptation. Liu et al. [24] introduced a scenario of UAVs providing on-demand full communication coverage, ensuring the minimization of the number of UAVs required for complete coverage. Lin et al. [25] introduced an iterative, adaptive UAV deployment and power control scheme that covers as many ground nodes as possible in emergencies while reducing communication power consumption. Liu et al. [26] proposed a scheme to dynamically adjust the UAV service radius by fine-tuning transmission power, aiming to minimize the number of UAVs deployed and optimize coverage for static users.

Dynamic UAV deployment strategies based on RL have shown greater potential in various UAV network applications. Wu et al. [27] developed a DRL approach using a spatial attention mechanism to adaptively deploy UAVs according to the distribution of ground user density. Luo et al. [28] considered a UAV deployment and content placement strategy centered on fixed-location but dynamically active ground users, utilizing K-means and Q -learning methods. Zhang et al. [9] examined the coverage issues for mobile users, considering the entry and exit of UAVs into the network for recharging or other reasons, using an RL method named deep deterministic policy gradient (DDPG), to maximize user satisfaction. Similarly, Guo et al. [29] also considered UAVs' entry and exit to accommodate the power constraints of the systems. Zhou et al. [30] proposed a multi-UAV network Quality of Experience (QoE)-driven, energy-saving adaptive deployment strategy based on DRL, suitable for serving randomly moving users in targeted areas. Our previous work [31] addresses UAV deployment, including movement and state transitions (active or inactive) in dynamic environments with fluctuating user requests. However, it lacks a detailed analysis of the tradeoff between power consumption and user coverage.

B. Motivation and Contributions

Existing works on UAV deployment do not sufficiently address problems in highly dynamic systems. Some works focus only on environments with users having fixed locations and static demands [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], aiming primarily to optimize UAV placement, quantity, or task execution sequences. While some works employ DRL-based strategies to address network dynamics, these typically focus on a single aspect of the system. For example, Zhou et al. [30] emphasized adaptive deployment to better cover mobile users, Luo et al. [28] primarily considered adaptation for users with fluctuating demands. Additionally, intermittent changes, such as UAVs entering or leaving the network, are often treated as isolated incidents rather than as part of ongoing dynamics [9]. Consequently, dynamic events are typically perceived as discrete occurrences, and state spaces are often cluttered with redundant data. This leads to two key challenges: first, the difficulty in developing strategies that can adapt to highly dynamic environments, where UAVs and users are in constant motion, while effectively managing both power efficiency and user coverage. Second, the design of state spaces in RL struggles to adequately capture and prioritize the most critical aspects of environmental variability, leading to inefficiencies and limited adaptability.

To tackle the mentioned problems, this article presents an innovative multi-UAV-assisted wireless network that dynamically deploys UAVs and adjusts their coverage radius in real-time in response to system variations caused by changes in the number and distribution of users. The contributions of this article are as follows.

- 1) This article consider a highly dynamic multi-UAV wireless network scenario with movable UAVs and users. This scenario considers the varying operational modes of UAVs and the fluctuating service demands of

users. The goal is to jointly optimize the UAVs' operational modes, transmission power levels, and movement strategies in order to achieve an effective tradeoff between minimizing power consumption and maximizing the ground user coverage.

- 2) To extract critical information in complex and dynamic environments, the state space is designed using multimodal features, including a multichannel image and two vectors. The image consists of the coverage maps of UAVs and density maps of users who need service, which captures environmental dynamics while filtering out irrelevant information, such as users who do not request service. The two vectors contain information about the UAVs' mode and position, as well as time information, respectively. These multimodal features are processed via CNN and MLP layers for in-depth feature extraction, with PPO ensuring stable parameter updates during DRL model training. The proposed RL model, enhanced by the multimodal feature state space and PPO, is named MFPPPO. Simulation results demonstrate that MFPPPO excels in UAV deployment within dynamic systems and improves energy efficiency.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows. Section II presents the system model and problem formulation of the proposed Multi-UAV-assisted wireless networks. Section III introduces the preliminary knowledge of RL. Section IV details the proposed MFPPPO algorithm. Section V provides a comprehensive overview of the experimental results. Finally, Section VI concludes this article.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

This section provides a detailed overview of the proposed system model for a multi-UAV wireless network, including the dynamic network environment and communication models. An optimization problem is then formulated, addressing user coverage and UAV power consumption in response to the dynamic environment.

A. Dynamic Network Environment

This article considers a resource-constrained wireless network scenario involving UAVs deployed dynamically to provide adaptive communication coverage. The network operates within a target area of size $L \times L$. The UAVs are represented by a set $\mathcal{U} = \{1, 2, \dots, U\}$ and indexed by u . These UAVs can dynamically adjust their positions, transmission power levels, and operational modes to meet the communication demands of ground users. Ground users are represented by a set $\mathcal{G} = \{1, 2, \dots, G\}$ and indexed by g . Real-time user positions and state information are collected through the existing communication infrastructure, enabling UAVs to respond to fluctuating service requirements. All UAVs are stationed at a central park located at coordinates $(L/2, L/2)$, from where they initiate their operations.

The system's dynamics are influenced by the movements of both UAVs and ground users, the variability of their states, and the UAVs' ability to adjust their coverage areas. The primary objective is to balance two goals: 1) maximizing

Fig. 1. Dynamic multi-UAV wireless network.

user coverage while minimizing power consumption, ensuring that the network remains efficient and 2) responsive under varying environment conditions. These dynamics are modeled over a specified time period T , divided into discrete time steps $t \in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}$. An overview of the system's adaptive adjustments and interactions is provided in Fig. 1. The specific system dynamics are outlined as follows.

1) *Movement*: The position of UAV $u \in \mathcal{U}$ at a time step t is denoted as $(x_u(t), y_u(t), z_u(t))$, where $z_u(t) = H$ denotes a constant altitude. At each time step t , UAV u moves in a direction $w_u(t)$ at a constant speed $v_u(t)$. Similarly, the position of the ground user $g \in \mathcal{G}$ at a time step t is given by $(x_g(t), y_g(t), z_g(t))$, where $z_g(t) = 0$ denotes the ground. Each user moves within the target area, adjusting their position according to the direction $w_g(t)$ and speed $v_g(t)$.

2) *State Transitions*: Ground users can be in one of two states, represented as $o_g(t) \in \{0, 1\}$. When $o_g(t) = 0$, the user is in the service request (SR) state at a time step t , indicating the need for communication support from a UAV. Conversely, $o_g(t) = 1$ denotes the no SR (NSR) state at a time step t , meaning no additional UAV services are necessary during that time step.

UAVs operate in one of three distinct operational modes, denoted as $o_u(t) \in \{0 \text{ (Docked)}, 1 \text{ (Idle)}, 2 \text{ (Active)}\}$.

1) *Active Mode*: UAVs are actively engaged in providing communication services to ground users. In this mode, they may adjust their positions and transmission power levels to optimize their coverage and maintain network efficiency.

2) *Idle Mode*: UAVs are airborne but not currently transmitting. They navigate toward the central park station, optimizing their power consumption while awaiting new SRs.

3) *Docked Mode*: UAVs are stationed at the central park station, inactive and ready for redeployment when needed.

3) *Coverage Tuning*: The coverage radius of a UAV represents the maximum horizontal distance in a 2-D plane at which the UAV can provide sufficient communication service.

Fig. 2. Radio propagation between a UAV and users in an urban environment.

This radius can be dynamically adjusted by tuning UAVs' transmission power. This flexibility allows the UAVs to expand or contract their coverage area based on the real-time density of users, enabling more energy-efficient network operations. The relationship between transmission power and coverage radius is formally explained in Section II-B2.

B. Communication Model

1) *Air-to-Ground Channel*: UAV-to-user communication is modeled using air-to-ground (ATG) propagation in an urban environment, following the approach proposed in [32]. This model accounts for both Line-of-Sight (LoS) and Non-LoS (NLoS) propagation paths, capturing the complexity of urban signal propagation. Fig. 2 illustrates the radio propagation between a UAV and ground users. The mean path loss for the ATG link is modeled as

$$PL_{\xi} = PL_{FS} + \eta_{\xi}, \quad \xi \in \{\text{LoS}, \text{NLoS}\} \quad (1)$$

where PL_{FS} is the free-space path loss calculated using the Friis equation, assuming isotropic antennas at both the transmitter and receiver. The term η_{ξ} represents the additional attenuation due to the urban environment, with ξ indicating the propagation condition, either LoS or NLoS. The path loss under LoS and NLoS conditions can be expressed as

$$PL_{\text{LoS}}[\text{dB}](d_{u,g}) = 20 \log_{10} d_{u,g} + 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{4\pi f}{c} \right) + \eta_{\text{LoS}} \quad (2)$$

$$PL_{\text{NLoS}}[\text{dB}](d_{u,g}) = 20 \log_{10} d_{u,g} + 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{4\pi f}{c} \right) + \eta_{\text{NLoS}} \quad (3)$$

where $d_{u,g}$ is the distance between the UAV u and the ground user g , f is the carrier frequency, c is the speed of light. At a time step t , the distance $d_{u,g}(t)$ is denoted as

$$d_{u,g}(t) = \sqrt{H^2 + (x_u(t) - x_g(t))^2 + (y_u(t) - y_g(t))^2}. \quad (4)$$

The probabilities of the LoS and NLoS paths are given by

$$P_{\text{LoS}}(d_{u,g}) = \frac{1}{1 + a \exp(-b(\psi - a))} \quad (5)$$

$$P_{\text{NLoS}}(d_{u,g}) = 1 - P_{\text{LoS}}(d_{u,g}) \quad (6)$$

where $\psi = \arcsin(H/d_{u,g})$ is the elevation angle between the UAV and the user, as shown in Fig. 2. a and b are environment-dependent parameters known as S-curve parameters [32]. The spatial expectation of path loss is denoted as

$$PL_e[\text{dB}](d_{u,g}) = P_{\text{LoS}}(d_{u,g}) \times PL_{\text{LoS}}(d_{u,g}) + P_{\text{NLoS}}(d_{u,g}) \times PL_{\text{NLoS}}(d_{u,g}). \quad (7)$$

2) *Transmission Power and Coverage Radius*: The coverage radius of a UAV depends on its transmission power, the path loss during communication, and the minimum received power required by ground users, also known as the receiver sensitivity. The minimum acceptable received power for ground users is denoted as P_g^{RX} . The coverage radius $\rho_u(t)$ on the ground is determined by the maximum distance d_{max} at which the received power from UAV u meets the minimum sensitivity requirement P_g^{RX} . This is calculated by

$$\rho_u(t) = \sqrt{d_{\text{max}}^2 - H^2}, \quad \text{if } P_u^{\text{TX}}[\text{dBW}](t) - PL_e(d_{\text{max}}) = P_g^{\text{RX}} \quad (8)$$

where P_u^{TX} is the transmission power of UAV u . Based on (8), the radius of a UAV can be adjusted by controlling its transmission power. A user g is considered covered at time t if there exists at least one UAV u such that the horizontal distance between them is less than or equal to the coverage radius $\rho_u(t)$. This is denoted as

$$\mathbb{I}_g(t) = \max_{u \in \{1, \dots, U\}} \left(\mathbb{I} \left(\sqrt{(x_u(t) - x_g(t))^2 + (y_u(t) - y_g(t))^2} \leq \rho_u(t) \right) \right) \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbb{I}(\cdot)$ is the indicator function that equals 1 if (\cdot) is true, and 0 otherwise. For each time step t , the total number of uncovered SR users, denoted as $n_{uc}(t)$, is calculated by

$$n_{uc}(t) = \sum_{g \in G} [(1 - \mathbb{I}_g(t)) \cdot \mathbb{I}(o_g(t) = 0)] \quad (10)$$

where the first term captures users who are not covered, and the second term ensures that only users in the SR state are counted.

Each UAV base station operates on a distinct frequency band to minimize communication interference. Orthogonal frequency division multiple access (OFDMA) is employed to efficiently manage the potential interference among users served by the same UAV. As a result, SR users are assigned to the nearest active UAV base station.

C. Power Consumption Model

The power consumption of UAV u at a time step t consists of two components: 1) flying power $P_u^F(t)$ and 2) transmission power $P_u^{\text{TX}}(t)$

$$P_u[\text{Watt}](t) = P_u^F(t) + P_u^{\text{TX}}(t). \quad (11)$$

This article examines the UAVs' adaptive coverage for ground users at each discrete time step. Thus, the UAVs' instantaneous

power is defined as the power consumption of each time step. The power required for flight, including both propulsion and hovering, is assumed to be constant, as the UAVs' movement strategy is optimized only through UAVs' movement direction in this article. This constant flying power is denoted by P_F . The flying power consumption across different states can be expressed by

$$P_u^F[\text{Watt}](t) = \begin{cases} P_F, & \text{if } o_u(t) = 1 \text{ or } o_u(t) = 2 \\ 0, & \text{if } o_u(t) = 0. \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

The transmission power per time step, denoted as $P_u^{\text{TX}}(t)$, is variable, but in docked and idle modes, it is zero. To express transmission power in the same units as flying power, the conversion is performed as

$$P_u^{\text{TX}}[\text{Watt}](t) = 10^{\left(\frac{P_u^{\text{TX}}[\text{dBW}](t)}{10}\right)}. \quad (13)$$

D. Problem Formulation

Based on the system model, this article explores a dynamic strategy for deploying UAVs in response to varying user activities. The strategy aims to ensure that the proper UAVs are activated and dispatched, and adjust their coverage areas to accommodate varying SR user numbers and densities. Our objective is to optimize the tradeoff between UAVs' power consumption while minimizing the total number of uncovered SR users over the entire period T , formulated as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}_1 : \min & \sum_{t=0}^T \left(\alpha n_{uc}(t) + \beta \left(\sum_{u=1}^U P_u^{\text{TX}}(t) + P_u^F(t) \right) \right) \\ \text{s.t. } \mathbf{C}_1 : & 0 \leq x_u(t), y_u(t), x_g(t), y_g(t) \leq L \\ \mathbf{C}_2 : & P_u^{\text{TX}}(t) \leq P_u^{\text{TX}}_{\max} \\ \mathbf{C}_3 : & P_u^F(t) \leq P_F. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The weights α and β are parameters designed to balance the tradeoff between user coverage and power consumption. \mathbf{C}_1 ensures that both UAVs and users remain within the boundaries of the target area. \mathbf{C}_2 and \mathbf{C}_3 limit the transmission power and flying power of each UAV to its maximum allowable value, respectively. Factors affecting the number of uncovered SR users and power consumption include operational modes of different UAVs, the positioning of active UAVs, their coverage radius, and their anticipatory responses to user movements. Given the complexity and multiobjective nature of the problem, a dynamic deployment strategy for UAVs is developed using DRL. The challenges arise from non-linear dynamics, interdependent variables, and time-varying constraints, which make traditional optimization methods impractical for real-time applications. DRL addresses these limitations by learning adaptive policies directly from the environment, enabling efficient, real-time decision-making without relying on extensive assumptions or problem reformulations.

III. PRELIMINARIES ON RL

RL is a framework that models decision-making problems where an agent learns to make decisions by interacting with an environment. This process is based on trial and error, where

the agent receives rewards as feedback for its actions, which can be either positive or negative. The primary components of RL include the *agent*, the decision-maker, and the *environment*, the system within which the agent operates. The interaction between the agent and the environment is cyclical. Initially, the agent observes the environment's current state, decides on an action, and then executes it. Following the action, the environment transitions to a new state and provides feedback or rewards to the agent based on the action's effectiveness. This sequence of actions and rewards continues, influencing the agent's subsequent decisions.

The mathematical framework used to describe RL problems is the Markov decision process (MDP) [33], detailed by a tuple (S, A, P, R, γ) . S and A represent the sets of possible states and actions, respectively. P is the transition probability function that predicts the next state, given the current state and action. R is the reward function, which gives the immediate reward $r(t+1)$ received after transitioning from state $s(t)$ to a new state $s(t+1)$ due to action $a(t)$. Each set of state and action leading to the next state with its corresponding reward, $\{s(t), a(t), r(t+1), s(t+1)\}$, is termed a *transition*. γ , the discount factor, quantifies the importance of future rewards. An *episode* in RL is typically a finite sequence of transitions, ending either when a terminal state is reached or after a defined number of steps, T . This sequence, known as a *trajectory*, is denoted by $\tau = \{s(0), a(0), r(1), s(1), \dots, s(T-1), a(T-1), r(T), s(T)\}$. The policy π , which guides the agent's actions based on perceived states, aims to maximize the expected cumulative reward or the *return*, denoted by

$$G(t) = \sum_{i=0}^{T-t-1} \gamma^i r(t+i+1). \quad (15)$$

The goal in RL is to discover the optimal policy π^* that maximizes the expected return over time. This can be formally expressed as

$$\pi^* = \arg \max_{\pi} \mathbb{E}_{\pi}[G(t)]. \quad (16)$$

The expected return for an agent in state s following policy π is represented by $V^{\pi}(s) = \mathbb{E}_{\pi}[G(t)|S(t) = s]$, which is known as the state-value function. Similarly, the action-value function, denoted as $Q^{\pi}(s, a) = \mathbb{E}_{\pi}[G(t)|S(t) = s, A(t) = a]$, quantifies the expected return following a specific action in a given state. Within RL, a critical approach involves identifying the optimal state-value function and using it to derive the optimal policy through (16). This approach, known as value-based methods, includes techniques such as deep Q -network (DQN) [34]. Another category of RL methods, known as policy-based methods, focuses on directly optimizing the policy by using the value function as an objective function. These methods update the policy iteratively through policy gradient ascent to maximize this objective, exemplified by methods such as REINFORCE [35].

The AC method combines both policy-based and value-based approaches. This method incorporates value function estimation to guide policy updates and reduce variance. Typically, both the Actor and Critic are represented by deep neural networks, with parameters denoted by θ and

ϕ , respectively. The Actor interacts with the environment, producing a probability distribution of actions, represented as $\pi_\theta(a(t) | s(t))$. The Critic assesses the quality of actions under the current state, thereby helping the Actor update its policy. The Actor is updated based on the gradient ascent

$$\theta = \theta + l \sum \delta(t) \nabla_\theta \log_{10} \pi_\theta(a(t) | s(t)) \quad (17)$$

where l is the learning rate. $\delta(t)$ is the temporal difference (TD) error, which can be calculated by

$$\delta(t) = r(t+1) + \gamma V_\phi(s(t+1)) - V_\phi(s(t)). \quad (18)$$

The Critic is updated based on gradient descent

$$\phi = \phi - l \sum \delta(t) \nabla_\phi V_\phi(s(t)). \quad (19)$$

IV. DESIGN OF MULTIFEATURE-BASED DRL DEPLOYMENT APPROACH

This section outlines the proposed MFPPPO model. First, the design of the state, action space, and reward in the MDP is introduced, providing the foundation for the agent. Next, the structure of the MDP is presented, including state definitions, action space, and the reward function.

A. MDP Formulation

1) *State Space*: The state space defines the information that the agent utilizes to determine its actions, incorporating crucial details about the environment. The constructed state space consists of three main components, represented by

$$s(t) = \{\mathcal{I}(t), \mathcal{V}(t), \mathcal{L}(t)\}. \quad (20)$$

First, $\mathcal{I}(t)$ is a multichannel image that captures information on SR user distribution and UAVs' coverage area. The channels in $\mathcal{I}(t)$ are

$$\mathcal{I}(t) = \text{Stack}(\mathcal{D}(t), \mathcal{C}(t), \mathcal{D}(t-1), \mathcal{C}(t-1)) \quad (21)$$

where \mathcal{D} represents the density map of SR users, and \mathcal{C} indicates the UAV coverage map, as illustrated in Fig. 3(c) and (d). To simplify the state space, the target area is divided into an $M \times N$ grid, with each grid cell's size being the distance a UAV can move in a single time step. The first channel $\mathcal{D}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}$, where $\mathcal{D}_{(m,n)}(t)$ denotes the number of SR users per grid cell at (m, n) . Fig. 3(a) and (c) shows the original distribution of users and the abstracted density map, respectively. Similarly, the UAV coverage map $\mathcal{C} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}$ is detailed in Fig. 3(d), where $\mathcal{C}_{(m,n)}(t)$ represents the number of UAVs can cover the grid cell (m, n) . Furthermore, including maps from the previous moments $\mathcal{D}(t-1)$ and $\mathcal{C}(t-1)$ allows the agent to track temporal changes in user density and UAVs' coverage area. The *Stack* function combines these maps into a comprehensive multichannel image, yielding $\mathcal{I}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times M \times N}$. This multichannel image $\mathcal{I}(t)$ effectively captures the dynamic fluctuations in SR user numbers and UAVs' coverage ability, offering a high-level environmental feature that agents can utilize to make informed decisions.

Second, $\mathcal{V}(t)$ represents the vector feature, containing both position and operational mode information of the UAVs

$$\mathcal{V}(t) = \text{Stack}(\mathcal{V}_p(t), \mathcal{V}_p(t-1), \mathcal{V}_o(t), \mathcal{V}_o(t-1)). \quad (22)$$

Fig. 3. Multichannel image in state space. (a) Users distribution. (b) UAVs position and mode. (c) SR user density map $\mathcal{D}(t)$. (d) Coverage map of UAVs $\mathcal{C}(t)$.

In this equation, $\mathcal{V}_p(t)$ is the vector representing the positions of the UAVs in the grid, expressed as

$$\mathcal{V}_p(t) = \{x'_0(t), y'_0(t), x'_1(t), y'_1(t), \dots, x'_U(t), y'_U(t)\} \quad (23)$$

where $(x'_u(t), y'_u(t))$ denotes the grid coordinates of the UAVs. These are computed as $x'_u(t) = \lfloor [x_u(t)/l_g] \rfloor$, $y'_u(t) = \lfloor [y_u(t)/l_g] \rfloor$, where $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ denotes the floor function, rounding down any noninteger value to the nearest integer, and l_g is the length of each grid cell. Consequently, $x'_u(t) \in \{0, 1, \dots, M-1\}$ and $y'_u(t) \in \{0, 1, \dots, N-1\}$. $\mathcal{V}_o(t)$ is the vector of UAVs's operational modes, denoted as

$$\mathcal{V}_o(t) = \{o'_0(t), o'_1(t), \dots, o'_U(t)\} \quad (24)$$

where $o'_u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is a 3-D vector derived from the UAV's operational mode $o_u(t)$ via an embedding layer. This embedding layer assigns each categorical mode a learned vector representation [36], capturing its inherent relationships with other modes. By mapping similar modes to vectors positioned closely in the embedding space, their behavioral patterns can be effectively encoded. This process allows the model to better generalize across modes and enhances decision-making by providing a compact and meaningful representation of UAV operational states, which aids in subsequent learning tasks.

Third, $\mathcal{L}(t)$ represents the remaining time steps vector, obtained by applying a linear transformation to the remaining time steps, $T-t$, of the current episode. The scenario concludes at time T , defining a finite episode with a fixed number of steps. Including the countdown of remaining time steps in the state space helps stabilize the training process and enhances performance, as supported by [37].

Fig. 4. Model architecture of MFPPPO: multimodal feature extractor, actor, and critic network.

The state space incorporates multiple data modalities, including images and vectors, to offer a comprehensive representation of the environment, crucial for the agent's decision-making. It assumes reliable access to detailed information about users and UAVs, supported by current communication systems. For example, base stations can provide user location data [24], users can upload relevant information when requesting services [38], and UAVs can exchange data for effective coordination [39].

2) *Action Space*: The action space defines the decisions made by the agents, which in our system consist of three components of UAV actions: 1) movement direction; 2) operational mode; and 3) transmission power. The movement direction $w_u(t)$ of a UAV at a time step t is discretized to $w'_u(t) \in \{0, 1, \dots, 8\}$, where 0 signifies hovering in place, and the other values indicate movement in one of eight possible directions, defined as $w'_u(t) \times \pi/4$ radians on a 2-D plane. The movement step length $v'_u(t)$ of UAVs is fixed to one grid cell within the \mathcal{C} . The operational mode of the UAV u is denoted as $o_u(t) \in \{0, 1, 2\}$. The transmission power $P_u^{\text{TX}}(t)$ is discretized into three distinct levels, each corresponding to different coverage ranges, as visualized in Fig. 3(d).

Since transmission power adjustments are only applicable when UAVs are in an active mode, the operational modes and power adjustments in the action space are integrated into newly defined modes

$$\mathcal{M}_u = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{active mode with power level 1} \\ 1, & \text{active mode with power level 2} \\ 2, & \text{active mode with power level 3} \\ 3, & \text{idle mode.} \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

The docked mode is excluded from \mathcal{M}_u , as the UAV can only dock at the park station if it is able to reach the station in the next time step. In idle mode, the UAV's direction is oriented toward the park station, and the mode transitions to docked when $\mathcal{M}_u(t) = 3$ and the UAV can reach the station

in the subsequent step. This mode reconfiguration simplifies the action space, and the final action space for the agent is defined as

$$a(t) = \{w'_u(t), \mathcal{M}_u(t)\}_{u \in \mathcal{U}}. \quad (26)$$

3) *Reward*: The reward function provides essential feedback from the environment, guiding the agent toward finding the optimal policy. At each time step t , the reward is structured to encourage UAVs to minimize the number of uncovered SR users while optimizing power consumption. The reward function is defined as

$$r(t) = -\alpha \frac{n_{uc}(t)}{n_g(t)} - \beta \frac{\sum_{u=1}^U P_u^{\text{TX}}(t)}{\sum_{u=1}^U P_{u \max}^{\text{TX}}} - \beta \frac{\sum_{u=1}^U P_u^F(t)}{\sum_{u=1}^U P_{u \max}^F} \quad (27)$$

where $n_g(t) = \sum_{g=1}^G \mathbb{I}(o_g(t) = 0)$ represents the total number of SR users at a time step t . The maximum flying power is denoted as $P_{u \max}^F = P_F$. Negative rewards are assigned to both the number of uncovered SR users and power consumption, as the RL agent aims to maximize the cumulative reward. Each component of the reward function is normalized to promote stable and efficient training. Transmission and flying power are treated separately to account for potential large differences in their values, allowing both to be optimized effectively.

B. MFPPPO

This section details the architecture and training methodology of the proposed MFPPPO model. The multimodal feature extraction network is introduced first, followed by an explanation of the clip mechanism within the PPO algorithm. Finally, an overview of the complete algorithmic process and its training procedure is provided.

1) *Multimodal Feature Extraction Network Architecture*: A feature extraction network composed of various network architectures is tailored for multimodal data in the state $s(t)$. As depicted in Fig. 4, the image input $\mathcal{I}(t)$ is processed using

a CNN framework, which subsequently flattens the output into a 1-D vector. For the UAV information $\mathcal{V}(t)$, an MLP, a feed-forward neural network capable of extracting features through multiple hidden layers, is utilized. Additionally, the remaining time steps $\mathcal{L}(t)$ are transformed into a vector through a single-layer, linear fully connected layer. These processed vectors from the three components are then stacked into a unified vector that serves as the input for subsequent network layers. Furthermore, both the Actor and Critic models share this feature extraction network, optimizing the processing pipeline and reducing redundancy.

2) *Training of the MFPPPO*: PPO is employed to train agents in environments with multidimensional discrete action spaces due to its stable performance and robust results. AC methods update their policy based on (17), which can be unstable due to their reliance on noisy gradient estimates from the environment, leading to large and erratic updates to the policy. To address these problems, trust region policy optimization (TRPO) was developed, introducing a constraint that limits policy updates to a small predefined range to maintain stability [40]. PPO builds on TRPO's framework but simplifies it by using a clipped surrogate objective that constrains the policy update ratio, preventing significant deviations from the current policy. In PPO, the policy update rule is adjusted to include a clipping mechanism within the objective function

$$L_{\theta}^{\text{CLIP}} = \mathbb{E}(t) [\min(\kappa_{\theta}(t)\hat{A}(t), \text{clip}(\kappa_{\theta}(t), 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon)\hat{A}(t))] \quad (28)$$

$$\kappa_{\theta}(t) = \frac{\pi_{\theta}(a|s)}{\pi_{\theta_{\text{old}}}(a|s)}. \quad (29)$$

The $\kappa(t)(\theta)$ represents the ratio of the new policy probability to the old policy probability for taking action $a(t)$ in the state $s(t)$, and ϵ is a small positive number. The $\hat{A}(t)$ is known as generalized advantage estimation (GAE) [41], formulated as

$$\hat{A}(t) = \sum_{z=0}^{T-t-1} (\gamma\lambda)^z \delta(t+z) \quad (30)$$

where λ is a hyperparameter that helps balance bias and variance in the advantage calculations. The utilization of GAE helps PPO to smooth out the estimation of the advantage over a sequence of states and rewards, thus providing a more stable and consistent gradient for the policy updates. This approach integrates information over multiple steps rather than relying solely on immediate next steps, allowing for a richer and more robust dataset to guide the learning process. The entire training processing is concluded in Algorithm 1.

V. NUMERICAL RESULTS

This section presents the numerical results to demonstrate the performance of the proposed MFPPPO. First, the details of the parameters used in the experiments are provided. Next, the capability of MFPPPO to handle dynamic events in the system model is evaluated. Subsequently, user coverage and power consumption of MFPPPO are analyzed under different balance factors and varying numbers of UAVs. The performance of MFPPPO is then compared with other algorithms. Following

Algorithm 1 MFPPPO Training

- 1: Initialize Actor network parameters θ_0 and Critic network parameters ϕ_0 .
- 2: **for** each iteration $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ **do**
- 3: Collect trajectory data

$$\tau = \{s(0), a(0), r(1), s(1), \dots, s(T-1), a(T-1), r(T), s(T)\}$$

by executing policy π_{θ_k} in the environment.

- 4: Compute return $G(t)$.
- 5: Compute GAE $\hat{A}(t)$ based on the current value network V_{ϕ_k} .

$$\hat{A}(t) = \sum_{z=0}^{T-t-1} (\gamma\lambda)^z \delta(t+z)$$

$$\delta(t) = r(t+1) + \gamma V_{\phi_k}(s(t+1)) - V_{\phi_k}(s(t))$$

- 6: Optimize the PPO-clip objective via stochastic gradient ascent:

$$\theta_{k+1} \leftarrow \theta_k + l_{\theta} \nabla_{\theta} L_{\theta}^{\text{CLIP}}$$

- 7: Update the critic by minimizing the mean squared error of value predictions via gradient descent:

$$\phi_{k+1} \leftarrow \phi_k - l_{\phi} \nabla_{\phi} (V_{\phi_k} - G(t))^2$$

- 8: **end for**
-

this, the impact of UAV altitude on coverage is investigated. Finally, additional cases are explored to assess the robustness of the model.

A. Simulation Settings

The communication-related parameters f , a , b , and $(\eta_{\text{LoS}}, \eta_{\text{NLoS}})$ are set based on the simulations from [32] and [42]. The three discrete power levels P_u^{TX} in the action space are set at 3.49, 8.59, and 16.24 mW, corresponding to coverage radius ρ of 212.13, 353.55, and 494.97 m, respectively. To map this onto the coverage map $\mathcal{C}(t)$ in the state space, the coverage area is defined as the inscribed square within the coverage radius. This results in coverage areas ρ' of 3×3 , 5×5 , and 7×7 grid cells, centered on the UAV's position. In image state space $\mathcal{I}(t)$, the designated target area is structured as an $M \times N = 15 \times 15$ grid. The UAVs move at a constant speed of one grid cell per time step. The main parameters are summarized in Table I.

The UAVs are initially stationed at the park in docked mode. Users are uniformly distributed across the target area, starting in the NSR state at initialization. Their movement and state are modulated by following predefined events, each represented by an event center.

- 1) *Stability Intervals*: Users retain their current SR or NSR state during these periods and move in a random direction at a speed of $v_g = 20$ m/step.

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value	Description
G	100	The default number of users
U	4	The default number of UAVs
H	100	The default flying altitude of UAVs [m]
L	1500	Target area length [m]
l_g	100	Length of a grid cell [m]
M, N	15, 15	Grid dimensions in the state space
v_u	1	UAVs' speed in one time step [grid cell/step]
v_g	20, 100	Users' speed in one time step [m/step]
f	2	Centre carrier frequency [GHz]
α, β	1, 9	The default balance factors
$(\eta_{\text{LoS}}, \eta_{\text{NLoS}})$	1.0, 20.0	Pathloss pair in urban area [dB]
a, b	9.61, 0.16	S-curve parameters
P_F	50	Flying power consumption of UAVs [W]
P_i^{TX}	3.49, 8.59, 16.24	Discrete transmission power levels of UAVs [mW]
P_g^{RX}	-100	Users' receiver sensitivity [dBm]
ρ^g	3, 5, 7	Coverage grid cells [grid cells]
T	20	Episode length [time steps]
$\epsilon, \gamma, \lambda$	0.2, 0.99, 0.95	PPO parameters

TABLE II
SEQUENCE OF USER EVENTS

Time Steps t	Event Type	Coordinates and Radius
1	Mass Login	$(x_e = 400, y_e = 1100, r_e = 400)$ $(x_e = 1100, y_e = 400, r_e = 400)$
5	Mass Login	$(x_e = 400, y_e = 400, r_e = 400)$ $(x_e = 1100, y_e = 1100, r_e = 400)$
9	Mass Logout	$(x_e = 400, y_e = 1100, r_e = 400)$ $(x_e = 1100, y_e = 400, r_e = 400)$
13-16	Attraction	$(x_e = 400, y_e = 400, r_e = 450, r_c = 50)$ $(x_e = 1000, y_e = 1000, r_e = 450, r_c = 50)$
16	Mass Logout	$(x_e = 1100, y_e = 1100, r_e = 400)$
16-20	Dispersion	$(x_e = 400, y_e = 400, r_e = 300)$

- 2) *Mass Login*: This event activates users within a specified area, switching them to SR state.
- 3) *Mass Logout*: This event deactivates users within a specified area, switching them to the NSR state.
- 4) *Attraction Event*: This event draws users toward a point of interest within a specified radius, simulating high-activity zones. Users move toward these points at an increased speed of $v_g = 100$ m/step. To prevent all users from converging on a single point, a central radius is defined within the attraction event. Once users enter this area, their movement shifts to stability intervals, avoiding further convergence.
- 5) *Dispersion Event*: This event prompts users to move away from specific points of interest within a defined radius. It simulates conditions where users naturally disperse from congested areas or evacuate in response to emergencies. Users' speed is also $v_g = 100$ m/step.

Except for stability intervals, other events are defined by an event center point (x_e, y_e) and an event radius r_e . For Attraction events, an additional center radius r_c is defined. These mechanisms dictate the dynamics of SR user numbers and spatial density. A sequence of user events is designed, as detailed in Table II. Users outside the defined event time steps are considered to be in stability intervals. Similarly, users located outside the event radius during an event behave the same as they would during stability intervals. If users are located within the radius of multiple events, they will respond to the nearest event center.

Fig. 5. Number of SR users and active UAVs over time steps.

B. Result Analysis

Fig. 5 illustrates the number of SR users and active UAVs across time steps. This figure highlights the MFPPPO's ability to dynamically adjust UAV deployment in response to fluctuations in user activity. There is a distinct correlation where increases in the number of SR users, marked as Mass login, are met with proportional increases in active UAVs, demonstrating the system's capability to scale up operations to meet rising demands. Conversely, the Mass logout events show a significant reduction in both users and UAVs, reflecting the system's efficiency in scaling down UAVs when demand wanes. The rapid adjustments in UAV deployment in response to both increases and decreases in user activity underscore the system's robust adaptive control and predictive capabilities, ensuring that UAV availability is precisely aligned with user needs at all times. A proactive adjustment of UAVs is observed during the second mass login event, where deployment anticipates the increased demand. This analysis reveals that the MFPPPO system is not only reactive but also proactive in managing UAV resources and optimizing operational efficiency in real-time user environments.

Fig. 6 offers a detailed visual analysis of user distribution captured at various time steps. The series of snapshots shown in Fig. 6(a) through (d) illustrate significant shifts in user density during the Attraction and Dispersion events. During the Attraction events [Fig. 6(a) and (b)], users cluster around certain attraction points within a specific radius (shown as circles in the figure). These points draw a higher density of SR users. Conversely, the Dispersion events [Fig. 6(c) and (d)] display that the users spread out, moving away from a central dispersion point. Fig. 7 focuses specifically on the transmission power consumption of UAVs during the Attraction and Dispersion events. The two UAVs in the figure are responsible for the areas where these events occur. This figure primarily demonstrates how UAVs adjust their transmission power in response to user density changes. There are noticeable reductions in UAVs' transmission power after the time steps corresponding to the Attraction and Dispersion events. This reduction is strategic, conserving power when user density is concentrated in a smaller coverage area. Conversely, transmission power consumption increases during the Dispersion events as UAVs extend their transmission power to maintain connectivity over a larger area, accommodating the more spread-out distribution of users. This demonstrates the

Fig. 6. User density under different events: snapshots at various time steps. (a) Attraction events, at $t = 14$. (b) Attraction events, at $t = 15$. (c) Dispersion events, at $t = 16$. (d) Dispersion events, at $t = 17$.

Fig. 7. Transmission power consumption of UAVs over time steps.

Fig. 8. Tradeoff between the cumulative outage rate and power consumption with different α values.

MFPPO's capacity to dynamically adjust UAVs' transmission power settings in response to user distribution, optimizing both power consumption and coverage.

Fig. 8 illustrates the tradeoff between the user coverage and total power consumption as the reward balancing factor α increases from 1 to 13, with the power consumption coefficient β held constant at 1. User coverage is measured by the outage rate, where the outage rate at a time step t , denoted as $r_o(t) = [n_{uc}(t)/n_g(t)]$, measures the proportion of uncovered SR users relative to the total SR users. At the start ($t = 0$), all users are in the NSR state, so $r_o(0) = 0$. The cumulative outage rate over the entire episode is given by $R_o = [\sum_{t=1}^T n_{uc}(t)/\sum_{t=1}^T n_g(t)]$. As α grows, the system increasingly prioritizes user coverage over power conservation. At $\alpha = 1$, power consumption dominates, leading to a scenario where no UAVs are deployed and all users remain uncovered.

Fig. 9. Training curves of MFPPO agent across different α values.

As α increases, the cumulative outage rate decreases, but power consumption rises correspondingly. Notably, when α exceeds 7, power consumption continues to increase while the reduction in cumulative outage rate becomes minimal, indicating the UAVs have reached their coverage capacity limits, with further power expenditure offering limited improvement in coverage.

Fig. 9 illustrates the training curves of the MFPPO agent for various values of α over training steps, with the y-axis representing the mean episode return. The relatively small difference in the final convergence values is due to the normalization of the reward function components. This normalization ensures that the agent's learning process remains stable, even when the weighting factors are adjusted. For the case of $\alpha = 1$, the training curve shows some fluctuation, primarily due to the agent's exploration behavior. The value $\alpha = 1$ is a special case because it causes the agent to avoid deploying UAVs. Whenever the agent attempts to explore UAV deployment, it results in lower returns. In contrast, when α takes on other values, the convergence curves are smoother and more stable.

Next, the performance of MFPPO is evaluated and compared with several other methods, including Static deployment, the RL-based algorithms AC and TRPO, and traditional optimization methods GA and PSO. In the Static deployment,

Fig. 10. Time-step outage rate in an episode of different algorithms, with $\alpha = 9$ and $\beta = 1$.

Fig. 11. Power consumption in an episode of different algorithms, with $\alpha = 9$ and $\beta = 1$.

4 UAVs are activated at the first time step and distributed symmetrically at the midpoints of the edges of the square target area: $(\lfloor M/4 \rfloor, \lfloor N/4 \rfloor)$, $(\lfloor M/4 \rfloor, \lfloor 3N/4 \rfloor)$, $(\lfloor 3M/4 \rfloor, \lfloor N/4 \rfloor)$, and $(\lfloor 3M/4 \rfloor, \lfloor 3N/4 \rfloor)$. These UAVs maintain their highest power level throughout the entire period T , aiming for stable coverage without consideration of power consumption. For GA and PSO, the fitness score is set according to the episode reward obtained from the environment. The GA is configured with a population of 2000, up to 500 generations, adaptive mutation and crossover rates, rank-based selection, multipoint crossover, multistage mutation. The PSO configuration uses a swarm size of 500 and a maximum of 200 iterations to maximize cumulative reward by optimizing UAV actions over the episode. As illustrated in Figs. 10 and 11, the GA and PSO result in high outage rates and power consumption. TRPO, while achieving the lowest outage rate, does so at the cost of significantly higher power consumption, especially after time step 10. Both MFPPPO and AC demonstrate a more balanced performance between power consumption and user coverage. Notably, MFPPPO achieves the lowest power consumption among all methods, making it the most efficient in terms of resource management while still maintaining adequate user coverage throughout the episode.

Additionally, the impact of varying the number of UAVs on system performance is examined. Fig. 12 demonstrates the effect of the number of UAVs on both the cumulative outage rate and the overall power consumption with the balancing parameter $\alpha = 9$ and $\beta = 1$. As the number of UAVs increases, the cumulative outage rate decreases steadily. However, when the number of UAVs reaches 4 or more, both the system's power consumption and coverage capability show minimal

Fig. 12. Impact of the number of UAVs on the cumulative outage rate and power consumption, with $\alpha = 9$ and $\beta = 1$.

Fig. 13. Coverage radius corresponding to different transmission power, and under different flying altitudes of UAVs.

further changes. This indicates that, under this parameter setting, deploying more than 4 UAVs offers little benefit in terms of coverage while significantly increasing power consumption. Therefore, the default number of UAVs is set to 4 in this article, as further deployment would be inefficient from a power-consumption perspective.

The impact of UAV flight altitude on coverage and deployment is further investigated. Using (8), the relationship between the transmission power P_u^{TX} and the UAV's ground coverage radius ρ_u is derived. In earlier experiments, the UAV's flight altitude was fixed at 100 m. Fig. 13 presents the relationship between transmission power and coverage radius for different flight altitudes H . It is evident that for the same transmission power, the coverage radius decreases as the altitude increases. Fig. 14 illustrates the outage rate over time steps for three different altitudes (100, 200, and 400 m) at fixed transmission power levels, listed in Table I. The results show that as altitude increases, the outage rate significantly increases as the transmission power remains constant.

To comprehensively assess the model's adaptability and robustness under varied user dynamics, five additional simulation cases are developed, each with distinct task durations and user event sequences. The time steps for these cases were randomly generated between 10 and 25, with varying event sequences and radii, as summarized in Table III. Default parameters of $\alpha = 9$ and $\beta = 1$ were used for all cases,

TABLE III
DIFFERENT DYNAMICS OF CASES

Case 1		Case 2		Case 3		Case 4		Case 5	
t	Events	t	Events	t	Events	t	Events	t	Events
1	Mass Login (550,550,300) (550,950,300)	1	Mass Login (950,550,400) (950,950,400) (550,550,300)	1	Mass Login (750,750,600)	1	Mass Login (400,400,500) (1000,1000,500) (400,1000,500)	1	Mass Login (950,950,300)
5-10	Dispersion (550,550,500)	5-10	Attraction (950,550,500,50) (550,550,400,50)	2-10	Attraction (1100,1100,500,50) (450,450,500,50)	5	Mass Logout (450,450,400)	5-10	Attraction (900,900,500)
5	Mass Logout (550,950,400)	10	Mass Logout (950,950,500)	10	Mass Logout (450,450,300)	10-15	Attraction (1000,500,600,50)	10	Mass Login (400,400,500) (1100,400,500)
10-13	Attraction (550,550,600,50)	13	Mass Logout (550,550,500)	10-15	Dispersion (1100,1100,400)	15	Mass Logout (1000,500,300)	10-15	Dispersion (950,950,400)
		10-16	Dispersion (550,550,400)	15-20	Mass Login (900,400,400)	15-18	Attraction (1000,1000,600,50)	20	Mass Logout (400,400,600) (1000,1000,500)
						18-22	Dispersion (1100,1100,400)	24-25	Mass Logout (1100,400,600)

Fig. 14. User outage rate corresponding to different flight altitudes of UAVs.

Fig. 15. Comparison of episode returns for different methods across various test cases.

with different algorithms evaluated for comparison. Fig. 15 presents the episode returns of different algorithms across simulation cases. Although the normalization of certain reward components slightly compresses the numerical differences, MFPPO consistently achieves the highest returns. In addition, Fig. 16(a) and (b) illustrates the cumulative outage rates and total power consumption for each case. Traditional methods, such as GA and PSO, display higher outage rates and power consumption compared to RL-based models. Among RL approaches, MFPPO demonstrates the best tradeoff between reducing outage rates and minimizing power consumption. While TRPO achieves a low outage rate in case 4 and case 5, it comes with significantly higher power consumption. In

Fig. 16. Performance comparison of different algorithms across various test cases. (a) Cumulative outage rate. (b) Total power consumption.

contrast, AC results in similar power levels to MFPPO but exhibits a slightly higher outage rate. These results highlight the superiority of MFPPO, outperforming both traditional and RL-based methods in achieving a balanced outcome between outage rate and power consumption.

VI. CONCLUSION

This article presents a novel approach for adaptive UAV deployment in dynamic multi-UAV wireless networks, jointly optimizing power consumption and user coverage. The proposed MFPPO model, which integrates a multimodal feature state space with PPO, enhances the UAVs' ability to adapt to rapidly changing environments. By effectively managing UAV operational modes, transmission power levels, and movement directions, MFPPO achieves a balance between minimizing user outage rate and reducing power consumption. Simulation results validate its effectiveness, demonstrating the model's potential as a robust solution for real-time UAV network management in dynamic settings. The RL model in this article assumes the agent has a comprehensive view of the environment. Future research will explore optimized UAV deployment in complex, dynamic systems with limited observational space. Additionally, future work will focus on refining the model and extending its application to more complex systems, including real-time altitude adjustments, advanced kinematic movements, and real-world implementation challenges.

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